

Cite this: DOI: 10.1039/xxxxxxxxxx

Polymer margination in uniform shear flows

Venkat Bala,^{*a} Colin Denniston,^{b‡a}

Received Date
Accepted Date

DOI: 10.1039/xxxxxxxxxx

www.rsc.org/journalname

We address the issue of polymer margination (migration towards surfaces) in uniform shear flows through extensive LBMD (lattice-Boltzmann molecular dynamics) simulations. In particular we consider the effect of monomer size, a on the chain's overall margination tendency for chains of length $N = 16, 32$ monomers in flows at multiple shear rates $\dot{\gamma}$. We observed higher margination of chains with larger radii monomers in comparison to smaller radii monomer chains of the same length N . We quantify this effect by considering various measures such as the distribution of the maximum extent of the chain into the channel bulk, z_m , distribution of its center of mass in the direction normal to the surface, z_c and the distributions of the chain's radius of gyration in directions parallel and perpendicular to the surface i.e R_x, R_y and R_z respectively.

The dynamics and migration properties of polymers in shear flows near surfaces has widespread technological and biological applications. For instance a good understanding of the chain's dynamics and migration tendencies in flows is crucial for applications such as targeted drug delivery agents, shear activated polymeric systems^{1,2} and self-healing smart materials to name a few. Polymer migration also plays an important role in several important biological processes such as hemostasis^{3–5}.

The glycoprotein vWF (Von Willebrand Factors), being one of the largest polymeric molecules found in the blood plasma is known to migrate towards blood vessel walls under high shear rates. This initial cross stream migration of the chain signals the beginning of the entire blood clotting cascade in ruptured blood vessels. Near the surface, due to the elevated shear rates vWF chains unfold exposing their binding sites and adhere to the surface providing a sticky interface for platelets to adsorb^{1,4,6–9}.

However other experimental and simulation works have also observed chain migration away from the surface in flows. For instance microfluidic experiments involving DNA molecules have observed a depletion region near the channel wall in flows^{10,11} indicating a net migration of chains away from the surfaces towards the channel centerline. In pressure driven flows, since the polymer chains stretch along the flow direction and loose conformational entropy, based on thermodynamic arguments one can argue that the chains will migrate towards the channel center line where the shear rate is a minimum. The thickness of the depletion layer has also been seen to increase with flow rate¹¹.

Thermodynamic models¹² and models based on kinetic theories^{13,14} have been proposed in efforts to explain the migration of chains. However several of the models either neglected the hydrodynamic interactions between the various polymer segments and with the no-slip wall entirely or included those effects only within certain approximations.

Recent microfluidic experiments of dilute solutions of fluorescently labeled λ -DNA in shear flow have revealed that molecules migrate away from the walls^{15,16}. Jendrejack *et al*^{17–20} performed Brownian dynamics of λ -phage DNA solution in a square micro-channel while incorporating hydrodynamic interactions between the monomers as well as between the monomers and channel walls. They found that the confinement of the chains significantly influenced the direction of its lateral migration in flow. When the channel width was much larger than the chain's free space radius of gyration, R_g , migration towards the channel centerline of the molecules was observed. It was also found that for highly confined cases the migration trend was reversed and the chains migrated towards the walls. Similar results have also been observed in other simulation works^{10,21–28} and have confirmed the importance of chain-wall hydrodynamic interactions and channel confinement in determining the direction of the chain's migration in flows.

Recent works involving studying the margination tendencies of micro/nano sized particles in blood flow at different shear rates for drug delivery purposes have addressed the effect of particle size and shape on their overall migration tendency. Lee *et al*²⁹ through capillary flow experiments observed that smaller nano/micron sized particles appeared to be more uniformly distributed throughout the tube in comparison with particles of larger sizes. Furthermore Muller *et al*³⁰, through 2D & 3D DPD (dissipative particle dynamics) and smoothed DPD (smoothed DPD)

^a Department of Applied Mathematics, The University of Western Ontario, London, Ontario, N6A 5B7, Canada E-mail: vbalasu8@uwo.ca

^b Department of Physics and Astronomy, The University of Western Ontario, London, Ontario, N6A 5B7, Canada E-mail: cdennist@uwo.ca

simulations showed that larger sized particles margined more in flow in comparison to smaller particles. They constructed the probability distributions of finding a particle within a certain distance from the surface and found that the margination probability decreased with particle size. The observations discussed so far highlight the importance of the role of hydrodynamic interactions in shear flow, and the particle's size and shape in determining its overall margination tendency.

In this work we revisit the issue of lateral migration of polymer chains in flows via hybrid LBMD (Lattice Boltzmann-Molecular Dynamics). We study the margination tendencies of single polymer chains of length N in Couette flow over a range of shear rates $\dot{\gamma}$ and in particular investigate the effect of monomer size, a on the chain's overall migration. We observe that polymer chains with smaller monomers show poor margination tendencies as compared to their larger counterpart. Furthermore we also find that shorter chains with larger radii monomers marginate more strongly compared to longer chains. Moreover in contrast to Poiseuille flows, as the shear rate is constant throughout the entire channel in Couette flows there is no real benefit for single monomers to migrate cross-stream³¹. We believe our observations in this work are therefore primarily a chain effect rather than effects at a single monomer level.

1 Simulation Model

In this work, using hybrid LBMD simulations we investigated the margination properties of individual polymer chains in Couette flow. Moreover we studied the effect of monomer size, a on the margination tendencies of the chains in flow. All our simulations were carried out using LAMMPS³² and we used a D3Q15 Lattice-Boltzmann (LB) model to accurately incorporate hydrodynamic interactions (particle/particle, particle/no-slip surface) in our system. We use nano-units in LAMMPS, where distances are in nm , time in ns , and mass in ag . In our simulations the LB fluid mediates the hydrodynamic interactions as well as acts as a heat bath for the particles immersed in it. Implementing thermal fluctuations in the LB fluid so that it reproduces the fluctuation-dissipation correctly has been described in detail in³³. Details pertaining to our implementation of this framework can be found in³⁴⁻³⁶. This model and implementation are now well-tested in many examples³⁷⁻⁴⁰, including polymers in solution^{34,41,42}.

We used a lattice spacing of $dx = 0.5nm$ and updated the entire fluid lattice every time step. Depending on the chain length i.e $N = 16, 32$ the simulation box dimensions were set to $(32, 60, 32), (60, 100, 32), nm$ respectively and a time step of $\Delta t = 30fs$ was used. Every simulation carried out was at least a minimum of 300ns in duration. Following Ollila et.al^{34,41}, in order to speed up the diffusive dynamics, the density of our fluid was set to 1/60 that of water at $T = 300K$ and we scaled its kinematic viscosity by a factor of 1.4. To study the effect of monomer size we considered two different radii values, $a = 0.7$ and $1.4nm$ and kept the same radii for all monomers in a given chain. All the monomers were taken to be neutrally buoyant in the LB fluid.

In LB simulations mesh effects can be a major source of error if not accounted for properly. Following³⁶, in our simulations each monomer was comprised of two types of MD atoms (a) a central

atom and (b) a spherical shell of N_v nodes. This configuration of atoms in a monomer is depicted in figure (1). The benefit of using

Fig. 1 (Left) Composite monomer of radius $a = 0.7nm$ with $N_v = 60$ (Right) Composite monomer of radius $a = 1.4nm$ with $N_v = 180$

such an approach is that it gives each monomer a hydrodynamic size independent of the fluid lattice spacing. All bonded/non-bonded interactions are mediated by the central atoms whereas the spherical shell nodes interact only with the LB fluid and mediate the hydrodynamic interactions. In our simulations every monomer was treated as a rigid body during integration. We choose the number of surface nodes, N_v such that the surface area per node for a monomer of radius a is always smaller than dx^2 i.e $4\pi a^2/N_v < dx^2$. This rule of thumb ensures that the surface is sufficiently discretized and there are no big gaps in the monomer. Lastly monomers are connected using the FENE bond style,

$$U_b = -\frac{1}{2} K R_0^2 \log \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{R_0^2} \right) + 4\epsilon \left(\left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^6 + 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

with parameters $K = 60ag/nm^2$, $\epsilon = k_B T$, $\sigma_b = 1.5nm$ ($a = 0.7nm$), $2.67nm$ ($a = 1.4nm$) and $R_0 = 1.5\sigma_b$.

We used periodic boundary conditions in the x and y directions and fixed boundary conditions in the z direction. In all cases the system size is more than 2.5 times the equilibrium radius of gyration R_g of the chain so the chain is not compressed due to the slit geometry of the system. To mimic interactions with an impenetrable atomic surface we placed two layers of atoms in the tightly packed FCC 111 geometry with a lattice spacing of $1.0nm$ at the $z = 0$ boundary of the simulation domain as depicted in figure (2)

Fig. 2 Schematic of the wall atom geometry used in our simulations along with the LB lattice and surface interaction length scales

We implemented a 12 – 6 Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential of strength ϵ_w with interaction length scale σ_w between the central and wall atoms in our simulations. The monomer shell atoms and the fluid lattice sites were coupled via the method outlined in³⁶ to establish interactions between the two. Following⁴¹ and requiring that the gap size δ remains the same for different sized monomers when they are at the LJ surface potential minimum i.e a distance of $2^{1/6}\sigma_w$ from the bottom surface ($z = 0$) we set our LJ interaction length scale to $\sigma = 1.5\text{nm}$ for the $a = 0.7\text{nm}$ case and $\sigma_w = 2.12\text{nm}$ for the $a = 1.4\text{nm}$ case. Making the gap size, δ the same for both monomers meant that the lubrication forces between the wall and the particles depended only on the monomer radius and not on the differences between the distance from the wall, which in principle would be the same in absence of hydrodynamics. Given the FCC geometry of the surface and the different interaction length scales σ_w in our simulations, an individual monomer can interact with a different number of surface atoms depending on it's size. To ensure we are comparing otherwise equivalent systems, the surface potential interaction strength ϵ_w was tuned so that the adsorption tendencies of the $a = 0.7$ and 1.4nm chains were similar in equilibrium. Setting the surface interaction strength ϵ_w to 0.24 in the 0.7nm case and $\epsilon_w = 0.15$ in the 1.4nm case resulted in good agreement in the respective equilibrium adsorption tendencies, as demonstrated below. The surface interaction cutoff was placed at $r_c = 2.5\sigma_w$ for the both cases.

Fig. 3 (a) Probability distribution of the average number of monomers within a distance of $d_c = (26/7)^{1/6}\sigma_w$ from the surface, ϕ for $Wi = 0$. (b) Probability distribution of the chain's center of mass normal to the surface z_c scaled by the interaction length scale, σ_w . The fluctuations in the curves are due to statistical errors in the measurements.

To verify the equivalence of the interaction with the wall, in figure (3) we plot the distribution of two parameters that characterize the equilibrium adsorption tendencies of a single $N = 32$ monomer long chain. In figure (3a) we consider the distribution of ϕ which simply measures the fraction of monomers within a distance d_c from the surface. We chose the inflection point of the LJ potential as a suitable distance for this measure i.e $d_c = (26/7)^{1/6}\sigma_w$. For the aforementioned values of the interaction potential strength ϵ_w from this figure we can note that the agreement between the two ϕ distributions is very good. As a second measure of adsorption in equilibrium, in figure (3b) we plot the probability distribution of the chain's center of mass normal to the surface scaled by the respective interaction length scale, σ_w . Even though the data is a bit noisy in this figure we can see that the agreement between the two distributions is very good and the adsorption behavior for the chains in equilibrium is essentially identical.

We carried out simulations over a range of shear rates, $\dot{\gamma}(\text{ns}^{-1}) = 0, 0.2, 1.0, 2.0$. As a dimensionless measure of the shear rate, we scaled these values to their respective **Weissenberg Number**, Wi by simply multiplying them by the relaxation time of the principal Rouse mode of the chains. In the Zimm model, this is expected to follow⁴³

$$\tau_1 \sim \frac{\zeta N^{\nu} b^2}{3\pi^2 k_B T}. \quad (2)$$

Here ζ is the frictional coefficient for a single monomer in the solvent i.e $6\pi\eta a$, N is the number of monomers comprising the chain, b is the average bond length between the monomers, and $\nu \approx 1.74$ ³⁴. For better ensemble averaging we did at least five independent runs at each value of Wi . A Couette flow profile was generated by translating the top wall of our simulation domain parallel to the bottom surface in the positive y direction. This generated, on average a uniform shear flow profile in the channel. Lastly in all the runs the polymers started off near the bottom surface however all the results discussed in the following sections were computed after an equilibration period of at least 10^6 steps. A sample starting configuration of a chain is depicted in figure 4

Fig. 4 Sample of an initial conformation of the polymer on the surface. Note that for better depiction of the chain's conformation without overlapping of atoms we omit drawing the spherical shell surrounding each monomer

1.1 Monomer/Fluid coupling

As the monomers move through the fluid an interaction between the two must occur. Stokes law dictates that the fluid drag force

acting on a sphere is proportional to its velocity through the medium. In our LB algorithm we exploit this fact to couple the fluid and particles together by making the fluid drag force acting on a particle node proportional to its velocity relative to that of the fluid velocity interpolated to its location i.e

$$\mathbf{F}_i = -\gamma(\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_f) \quad (3)$$

However its important to note that proportionality constant, γ in (3) is not the Stokes drag coefficient $6\pi\eta a$ in general and has to be calibrated properly to ensure proper dynamics, thermalization and consistency between different measures of the hydrodynamic radii. The calibration procedure for the coupling parameter, γ is discussed in great detail in³⁶ and we follow it in this work to consistently set a value for γ . In principle the value of γ should be infinite in order to ensure a no-slip boundary condition on the particle's surface, however since equation (3) represents a stiff term, large values of γ will likely render the numerical integration of the system unstable. Thus γ must be large enough so that the hydrodynamic radius of the sphere obtained by say measuring the drag force acting on it under uniform translation through the fluid, $a_{h,F}$ or by computing the torque acting on it when held stationary in shear flow, $a_{h,T}$ must be in good agreement with each other. In our work we saw good agreement between $a_{h,F}$ and $a_{h,T}$ for $\gamma > 0.02$ in both cases i.e $a = 0.7, 1.4$ nm. During the calibration runs we noted that setting the value of $\gamma > 0.11$ resulted in numerically unstable runs in the $a = 0.7$ nm case, however we were able to push γ to 0.15 in the $a = 1.4$ nm case. Both of these values are sufficiently larger than the lower bound of 0.02 and over these ranges good agreement between the different measures of the hydrodynamic radii was observed. Calibrating the coupling parameter γ this way also ensured that the MD particles feel the right fluid temperature and are thermostatted properly during simulations.

1.2 Particle Thermostatting

In equilibrium, the probability of finding a particle at a particular height above a no-slip surface solely depends on its potential energy, $U(z)$ at that location. This relation is determined by the Boltzmann's probability

$$p(z) = N \exp\left(-\frac{U(z)}{k_B T}\right) \quad (4)$$

where, N is simply a normalization constant. Interestingly if one can measure the position distribution of the particle a priori, by simply inverting (4) the potential energy landscape as a function of the particle's position can easily be determined. To eliminate the normalization factor N , we divide $p(z)$ by $p(z_0)$ evaluated at the potential minimum and solve for U

$$\hat{U} = \frac{U(z) - U(z_0)}{k_B T} = \log \frac{p(z)}{p(z_0)} \quad (5)$$

Since the particle's height above the surface can easily be obtained from its trajectory this is a very convenient method for ensuring the particles are being correctly thermostatted and the value of fluid parameter γ has been properly calibrated. This is a com-

mon technique used in TRIM based experiments (*Total Internal Reflection Microscopy*)⁴⁴⁻⁴⁹ and we use the same technique here to ascertain that all the monomers interacting with the fluid feel the correct temperature of 300K. For this purpose we considered the motion of a single monomer near the surface at $z = 0$ with the same surface interaction strength as mentioned earlier. To check that our LB fluid simulations produce the correct equilibrium results we also carried out Langevin runs of the same system with a damping constant of 1.4τ where $\tau = (m\sigma_w^2/k_B T)^{1/2}$ is the Lennard-Jones time scale. In figure (5 a) we plot the probability distribution of a single $a = 0.7$ nm monomer's elevation above the surface derived from the trajectories obtained from five independent runs. We note that the results obtained from the LB simulations are in good agreement with the distribution obtained from the Langevin simulations. Similarly as seen from figure (5 b) the agreement is equally good for the effective potentials, \hat{U} derived from inverting the position distributions plotted in (5 a). Based on these observations we can note that the monomer-fluid coupling parameter, γ has been calibrated properly and that the particles immersed in the LB fluid are properly thermostatted at a temperature of $T = 300K$.

Fig. 5 (a) Probability distribution of a single $a = 0.7$ nm monomer's elevation above the wall at $z = 0$ (b) Effective potential landscape sampled by these monomer obtained by inverting the Boltzmann distribution (4). Monomer-surface interaction strength was set to $\epsilon_w = 0.24$ in the 0.7nm to ensure similar adsorption behavior to the 1.4nm case in equilibrium. The interaction length scale was set to the $\sigma_w = 1.5$ nm as per the monomer radius

2 Results & Discussion

2.1 A single monomer

We first examine the effect of simple shear flow on a single monomer. We have already examined the equilibrium behavior of monomers in figure (5). In figure (6a) we plot the effective potential obtained for the same monomer in shear, $\dot{\gamma} = 1.0$ and observe almost no difference in the derived effective potential. Although the Boltzmann' probability for a particle is an equilibrium property, performing the same analysis in shear with essentially identical results demonstrates that the ambient fluid flow has very little influence on the likelihood of a finding a single monomer close to the surface. The same result is obtained for the 1.4 nm case in figure (6b).

Fig. 6 (a) Comparing the pseudo potential derived from the position distribution of a single 0.7 nm monomer in shear flow, $\dot{\gamma} = 1.0$ to its equilibrium counterpart. (b) Effective/pseudo potential(s) derived from the position distribution of a single $a = 1.4$ nm monomer in equilibrium and in shear $\dot{\gamma} = 1.0$. The surface interaction strength, ϵ_w , in this case was set to 0.15 and the interaction length scale, σ_w was set to 2.12 nm

This result is not really a surprise as a single sphere in a simple shear flow, in the absence of noise and any potential interactions with the wall, will typically simply follow a streamline⁵⁰. In the presence of walls, there is a small hydrodynamic force that, without noise, will eventually cause the sphere to move to the center of the channel⁵¹. However, in our simulations we have noise which means the sphere moves from the streamline it starts on due to diffusion. As we saw in figure (5) this allows the sphere to explore the full energy landscape in equilibrium. In shear, the results in figure (6) demonstrate that the presence of shear does not significantly affect this result. It should also be noted that,

based on⁵¹, any hydrodynamic force on a single monomer would be expected to move it away from the wall towards the center of the channel and that this tendency would be greater for the larger sphere. For nanometer sized particles, this effect is tiny and is overwhelmed by the thermal noise.

2.2 Max monomer height & Center of mass

To quantify the margination of our chains multiple parameters based on the monomer positions in the direction normal to the surface at $z = 0$ can be calculated. In all our simulations every 120 steps we saved the chain's conformations to disk and carried out our analysis using those trajectories. One of the ways we characterized the chain's margination was by analyzing the distribution of the maximum height attained by a single monomer, z_m for each sample configuration over the course of a simulation.

Fig. 7 Probability density of the maximum height of a single monomer above the surface in equilibrium, $Wi = 0$ (a) $N = 16$ (b) $N = 32$

In figure (7), we plot the probability distribution of z_m scaled by the surface interaction length scale, σ_w for both the different chain lengths, $N = 16, 32$ in equilibrium ($Wi = 0$). From these plots we can see that in both cases the distributions are mostly uniform across the entire channel width. This result indicates that the chains, regardless of the monomer sizes, display similar behavior in equilibrium. Moreover it should also be clear from these distributions that in absence of any flow the polymers do not show a strong tendency to adsorb onto the wall for any substantial period of time.

Now in order to address the effect of shear flow on the chain's margination, in figure (8) we plot the residual distribution,

Fig. 8 Residual distributions, $\Delta P(z_m/\sigma_w) = P_{Wi}(z_m/\sigma_w) - P_0(z_m/\sigma_w)$ of the maximum height attained by a single monomer away from the no-slip surface at $z = 0$ in shear. The four different plots are for the cases (a) $N = 16, a = 0.7 \text{ nm}$ (b) $N = 16, a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ (c) $N = 32, a = 0.7 \text{ nm}$ (d) $N = 32, a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ respectively. The statistical error in the measurement of the probability distribution for the equilibrium case is about 0.05 which sets a lower bound for the statistical error in the residuals plotted here.

$\Delta P_{Wi} = P_{Wi} - P_0$ versus z_m/σ_w which is basically the difference between the in-shear and equilibrium distributions. From figure (8) to begin with, we can note that in all cases the residuals distributions show a leftward shifting trend that indicates an apparent increase in the probability for z_m being within $z_m = 2$ to $4\sigma_w$ from the surface. Secondly the trend is also such that the peak heights increase with increasing Weissenberg number. Apart from these overall trends a closer look at the curves makes it apparent that monomer size has a noticeable impact on the residual distributions. By analyzing plots (8a,c) versus (8b,d) we can notice that in comparison to the $a = 0.7 \text{ nm}$ case, the shift in probability density towards lower values of z_m is stronger and clearer in the $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ case for both chain lengths, $N = 16, 32$. Even at the lowest non-zero shear rate the $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ monomer radii chain shows a significantly higher probability concentration in the $z_m = 2$ to $4\sigma_w$ range from the surface in comparison to its $a = 0.7 \text{ nm}$ counterpart (where the trend is barely visible above the statistical fluctuations). This trend can also be seen to hold true for higher shear rates and the larger monomer chains display a higher propensity for margination in shear. From the latter two figures, i.e (8c,d) we can again see evidence for stronger margination in shear for the larger monomer chain as well as for the longer chains.

Since we are measuring distributions of the maximum height attained by a single monomer such a trend illustrates that shear tends to compress the chain's normal extent into the bulk and causes them to attain flatter conformations on the surface. We also quantified the chain's lateral size by measuring its radius of gyration in the normal direction to the surface and observed similar trends. Results and discussion pertaining to the chain's size is carried out in a later section. Since the relaxation timescale of the principal Rouse mode, τ_1 scales with the monomer size due to its dependence on the drag coefficient, $\zeta = 6\pi\eta a$, and the bond length b , the apparent increase in the margination tendency of the larger monomer sized chains may be explained in the light of longer relaxation times. As the chains assume flatter and elongated conformations on the surface, despite being of the same length and under the influence of the same surface potential, larger monomers couple more with the background fluid flow, which eventually causes the chain to maintain its elongated state for longer durations. Such elongated conformational states result in a severe entropic losses which cause the chains to marginate more towards the surfaces as under such circumstances, it becomes energetically favorable for the chains. In an effort to see if this is the case we looked at the residual distributions all scaled individually by their respective Wi numbers but we were unable to achieve a reasonable collapse of the data suggesting there may be more to the effect than can be explained by scaling with the relaxation time of the polymer in equilibrium and in bulk.

Another related parameter to assess the chain's margination in shear is its center of mass normal to the surface, z_{cm} . In figure (9) we plot the residual distributions of the same scaled by the surface interaction strength, σ_w and observe trends very similar to the ones depicted in figure (8). In these figures, we only plot the $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ monomer case to illustrate the behavior. The strongest peaks observed in these distributions in figure (9) all seem to peak over the interval $(1.5, 3.0)\sigma_w$ and this is somewhat to be

Fig. 9 Chain's normal center of mass residual distribution, $\Delta P_{Wi}(z_{cm}/\sigma_w) = P_{Wi}(z_{cm}/\sigma_w) - P_0(z_{cm})$. The two different plots are for the cases (a) $N = 16, a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ (b) $N = 32, a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ respectively

expected since the minimum of the surface interaction potential lies well within that interval. From all the observations discussed in this and the previous subsections, it is reasonable to conclude that longer chains and chains with the larger monomers are more likely to remain within the vicinity of the surface in shear and tend to marginate better in comparison to the shorter and smaller radii monomer chains.

2.3 Radius of Gyration

In the previous sections, we saw larger monomer and longer chains had enhanced margination. To see why it is helpful to examine the chain's conformational behavior in shear. In shear and elongational flows, polymers undergo severe conformational changes as they stretch and relax along the shear direction and tumble end-to-end incessantly^{4,7,22,52-55}. On thermodynamic grounds, such dramatic conformational changes result in severe conformational entropy losses for the polymer as the flow prevents it from retaining the equilibrium conformations of a three-dimensional self-avoiding walk which is the entropy maximum³⁴) for a free polymer. In pressure driven flows this causes a tendency for net migration of the chain away from the surface towards areas of low shear rate where this effect is diminished i.e towards the channel center line. In a Couette flow, however due to the uniform shear rate across the channel, migrating away from the no-slip surface is not entropically helpful for the chains.

In this section, by looking the radius of gyration of the chains we investigate their unfolding in shear flow near the surface

and demonstrate that relative to the $a = 0.7 \text{ nm}$ case, chains with $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ sized monomers are somewhat more likely to be in the elongated conformations. Based on the earlier observations of relatively stronger margination tendencies of the $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ chains in shear such elongated and compressed conformations imply more monomers being adsorbed on the surface making the situation energetically favorable for the them, thus compensating somewhat for the entropic losses.

For quantifying the chain's conformation changes we computed its radius of gyration in the principal directions i.e R_x, R_y, R_z by simply computing the average extent of all the monomers relative to the chain's center of mass in either of the directions.

$$R_\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (R_{i,\alpha} - R_{c,\alpha})^2} \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha = x, y, z$, $R_{i,\alpha}$ is the i^{th} monomer's coordinate in direction α and $R_{c,\alpha}$ is chain's center of mass coordinate along the same (recall that the y -direction is along the flow and z is the direction normal to the wall). In our analysis we scaled all the gyration measurements in the x, y direction by the bulk gyration value $N^\nu a$ where $\nu \approx 0.588$ and used the surface interaction potential length scale σ_w to scale the gyration measure of the chain normal to the surface, R_z . To study the effect of shear we again compute the residual distributions, $\Delta P_\alpha = P_{Wi}(R_\alpha) - P_0(R_\alpha)$ for all the gyration measures. We plot the residual distributions of R_y and R_z in figures (10, 11). We omit the gyration results from the $\dot{\gamma} = 0.2$ shear rate case as no significant differences from the equilibrium case were observed.

In figure (10 a, c) we plot the residual distributions for the R_y and R_z gyration measures for the $N = 16, 32$ chains. We notice that the residuals are positive at larger values of R_y in both cases indicating the elongation of the chains along the shear direction. The corresponding negative residuals of ΔP_y at smaller values of R_y clearly indicate that the chains are less likely to be in compact configuration in this case. Furthermore, it is also interesting to note that the R_y residuals are always higher in probability at larger values of the R_y in the $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ case. From figure (10 b,d), the residual distributions for R_z show an opposite trend as the peaks move leftward towards smaller values of R_z . This indicates that the chains on average in shear are much more likely to be in conformations which are rather elongated along the shear direction and compressed laterally. Plotting the same distributions for the shear rate $\dot{\gamma} = 2.0$ in figure (11) we notice the same trends as before but more pronounced in nature.

Furthermore to ensure that the chains in shear were not in any *log-rolling*, states i.e extended mainly along the x direction, in figure (12) we plot the residual distributions of chain's the radius of gyration in the x direction i.e R_x for all the shear rates. First, it can be noted that the distributions for the $a = 1.4 \text{ nm}$ radii monomers are more pronounced in comparison to the $a = 0.7 \text{ nm}$ case indicating that larger monomers chains are affected by the shear flow more strongly. We also note that the distribution peak over smaller values of R_x indicating that in shear flow, the chain's extent in this direction becomes restricted as the chains tend to align more in the direction of the shear flow.

Fig. 10 Residual distributions of the radius of gyration of the $N = 16, 32$ chains in the direction parallel to the shear flow, R_y and normal to the surface. Blue line represent the $a = 0.7$ nm case whereas the dashed line represents the distributions obtained in the $a = 1.4$ nm case. Figure (a,c) Residual distribution for R_y for the $N = 16, 32$ chains in $\dot{\gamma} = 1.0$ respectively. Figure (b, d) Residual distribution for R_z for the $N = 16, 32$ chains in $\dot{\gamma} = 1.0$

Fig. 11 Residual distributions for the radius of gyration of the $N = 16, 32$ chains in shear flow, $\dot{\gamma} = 2.0$. Blue line represent the $a = 0.7$ nm case whereas the dashed line represents the distributions obtained in the $a = 1.4$ nm case. Figure (a,c) Residual distribution for R_y for the $N = 16, 32$ chains in $\dot{\gamma} = 2.0$ respectively. Figure (b, d) Residual distribution for R_z for the $N = 16, 32$ chains in $\dot{\gamma} = 2.0$

Fig. 12 Residual distributions for the radius of gyration of the chains in the x direction, R_x for all the non-zero shear rates. (a) $N = 16, a = 0.7$ nm (b) $N = 16, a = 1.4$ nm (c) $N = 32, a = 0.7$ nm (d) $N = 32, a = 1.4$ nm

From the residual distributions of R_z plotted in figures (10) and (11) we can note that the lateral extent of the chains is comparable to each other in both cases i.e $a = 0.7, 1.4$ nm as they all peak roughly over the same range of values for R_z and attain similar heights, whereas the distributions for R_y and R_x are more clearly different for the polymer with larger monomers. Overall, the results is that larger monomer and longer chains experience a greater loss of entropy in shear (i.e. the distribution of conformations is farther from the equilibrium distribution).

There a number of competing effects at play in this system. The first is the energy from the wall-monomer potential which favors adsorption onto the wall. However, to gain from this energy the polymer must first adopt a 2-dimensional configuration which obviously has reduced entropy compared to the typical 3-dimensional self-avoiding random walk the polymer prefers in equilibrium. Secondly, the shear exerts a hydrodynamic force on the monomers. This force is greater for larger particles as the hydrodynamic drag force is proportional to the particle size. There is also a hydrodynamic force between monomers. This effect is similar to particle entrainment in a fluid stream where larger particles have a much higher tendency to become entrained than smaller particles⁵⁶. These forces act to elongate the polymer along the flow direction and are larger for the larger monomers. Finally, there is the relaxation time of the polymer relative the shear rate, as typically captured by the Weissenberg number, Wi . When Wi is small, the polymer should have time to relax towards it equilibrium configuration and should therefore be less elongated compared to when Wi is high. For the same shear rate, the relaxation time of a polymer with larger monomers is expected to be larger, as described in Eq.(2) thus leading to a larger Weissenberg number. Note that this is distinct from the second point above which relates to the force felt by a monomer as opposed to how long it takes to respond to this force.

Once the polymer is elongated in shear and assumes something closer to a two (or one) dimensional structure, it may as well take advantage of the energetic effects that favor adsorption onto the wall. The caveat is that this is an equilibrium argument that is not guaranteed to hold in the out-of-equilibrium situation studied here. In particular, if the polymer is rapidly rearranging its configuration it may not have time to take advantage of the adsorption energy before it changes to a configuration where adsorption is less beneficial. Even if the desorbed state is short lived it could have a significant impact on the overall likelihood of adsorption. Again, in this case the slower response time of the larger monomers favors their adsorption over the smaller monomer chains.

3 Conclusions

In this work through extensive LBMD simulations, we have addressed the issue of polymer margination in Couette shear flows and have observed that monomer size plays a decisive role in the overall migration of the chains, either away or towards the channel walls. We have shown that the polymer chains comprised of larger radii monomers show a greater tendency to marginate in comparison to chains of same length however with smaller radii monomers. By measuring the probability distributions of the max extent of the chain into the channel bulk we were able to

note that although the general trend of increase in probability over lower values of z_m with increasing shear rate was present in all cases, the difference in the distributions were more significant and more highly peaked for the larger monomer radii cases and the longer chains. We also looked studied the effect of scaling all the z_m residual distributions with their respective Weissenberg number but we did not see a good collapse of the resulting data. It seems likely that such a scaling may still be possible but would require defining the Weissenberg number with a relaxation time other than that of the equilibrium polymer in bulk. We mention again that the effects observed in this work appear to be a *chain effect* since in Couette flows due to the constant shear rate across the channel, individual monomers do not benefit from any cross-stream migration that would take them towards the walls.

By studying the chain's conformations through its radius of gyration in the x, y, z directions we also observed that in the vicinity of the surface, regardless the size of the monomer, every chain's lateral extent into the channel bulk was roughly the same however, the larger monomer sized chains showed higher probability to retain their elongated states along the shear direction compared to their smaller counterpart. Since larger sized monomers couple more with the shear flow as they experience a larger shear gradient across their entire surface, experience greater hydrodynamic stresses and also due to the anisotropic nature of the monomer's mobility near the surface, motion of the chains get significantly retarded near the surface causing it to relax more slowly. This in turn causes the chains to remain in their elongated conformations for longer causing more monomers to become adsorbed onto the surface. Our observed results can potentially be used to provide a functional reason for the exceptionally large size of vWF monomers (each monomer is typically made up of 2050 amino acids) and long length ($\sim 20,000$ kDa) of vWF multimers which play a crucial role in the initial stages of hemostasis⁵⁷.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Natural Science and Engineering Council of Canada (NSERC) and Ontario Graduate Scholarships (OGS). Computational resources were provided by the Shared Hierarchical Academic Research Computing Network (SHARCNET) and Compute/Calcul Canada.

Notes and references

- 1 M. Hoore, K. Rack, D. A. Fedosov and G. Gompper, *Journal of Physics Condensed Matter*, 2018, **30**, 064001.
- 2 H. Chen, M. A. Fallah, V. Huck, J. I. Angerer, A. J. Reininger, S. W. Schneider, M. F. Schneider and A. Alexander-Katz, *Nature communications*, 2013, **4**, 1333.
- 3 K. Rack, V. Huck, M. Hoore, D. A. Fedosov, S. W. Schneider and G. Gompper, *Scientific Reports*, 2017, **7**, 1–12.
- 4 K. Müller, D. A. Fedosov and G. Gompper, *4th Micro and Nano Flows Conference*, 2014, 7–10.
- 5 M. Furlan, *Annals of Hematology*, 1996, **72**, 341–348.
- 6 S. W. Schneider, S. Nuschele, A. Wixforth, C. Gorzelanny, A. Alexander-Katz, R. R. Netz and M. F. Schneider, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 2007, **104**, 7899–903.
- 7 A. Alexander-Katz, M. F. Schneider, S. W. Schneider, a. Wixforth and R. R. Netz, *Physical Review Letters*, 2006, **97**, 1–4.
- 8 C. E. Sing and A. Alexander-Katz, *Biophysical Journal*, 2010, **98**, L35–L37.
- 9 C. E. Sing, J. G. Selvidge and A. Alexander-Katz, *Biophysical Journal*, 2013, **105**, 1475–1481.
- 10 J. P. Hernández-Ortiz, H. Ma, J. J. de Pablo and M. D. Graham, *Physics of Fluids*, 2006, **18**, 123101.
- 11 L. Fang, H. Hu and R. G. Larson, *Journal of Rheology (1978-present)*, 2005, **49**, 127.
- 12 A. B. Metzner, *Improved Oil Recovery by Surfactant and Polymer Flooding*, Academic Press, 1977, pp. 439–451.
- 13 J. H. Aubert, S. Prager and M. Tirrell, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1980, **73**, 4103–4112.
- 14 S. G., A. R. C. and J. M. S., *Journal of Polymer Science: Polymer Physics Edition*, 1982, **20**, 947–952.
- 15 Y. L. Chen, M. D. Graham, J. J. De Pablo, K. Jo and D. C. Schwartz, *Macromolecules*, 2005, **38**, 6680–6687.
- 16 L. Fang, H. Hu and R. G. Larson, *Journal of Rheology*, 2005, **49**, 127–138.
- 17 R. M. Jendrejack, E. T. Dimalanta, D. C. Schwartz, M. D. Graham and J. J. de Pablo, *Physical review letters*, 2003, **91**, 038102.
- 18 R. M. Jendrejack, D. C. Schwartz, J. J. De Pablo and M. D. Graham, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2004, **120**, 6315.
- 19 R. M. Jendrejack, J. J. De Pablo and M. D. Graham, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2002, **116**, 7752–7759.
- 20 R. M. Jendrejack, M. D. Graham and de Pablo J. J., *J.Chem.Phys.*, 2000, **113**, 2894.
- 21 S. Reddig and H. Stark, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2011, **135**, 165101.
- 22 S. Danioko and M. Laradji, *Physica A Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 2012, **391**, 3379–3391.
- 23 J. Park, J. M. Bricker and J. E. Butler, *Physical Review E - Statistical, Nonlinear, and Soft Matter Physics*, 2007, **76**, 1–4.
- 24 O. B. Usta, J. E. Butler and A. J. Ladd, *Physics of Fluids*, 2006, **18**, 031703.
- 25 R. Khare, M. D. Graham and J. J. De Pablo, *Physical Review Letters*, 2006, **96**, 9–12.
- 26 S. C. Kohale and R. Khare, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2009, **130**, 104904.
- 27 R. Chelakkot, R. G. Winkler and G. Gompper, *EPL (Europhysics Letters)*, 2010, **91**, 14001.
- 28 L. B. Weiss, A. Nikoubashman and C. N. Likos, *ACS Macro Letters*, 2017, **6**, 1426–1431.
- 29 T. R. Lee, M. Choi, A. M. Kopacz, S. H. Yun, W. K. Liu and P. Decuzzi, *Scientific Reports*, 2013, **3**, 1–8.
- 30 K. Müller, D. A. Fedosov and G. Gompper, *Scientific Reports*, 2014, **4**, 1–8.
- 31 G. Segré and A. Silberberg, *Nature*, 1961, **189**, 209–210.
- 32 S. Plimpton, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 1995, **117**, 1–19.
- 33 R. Adhikari, M. E. Cates, K. Stratford and a. J. Wagner, *EPL*

- (*Europhysics Letters*), 2004, **473**, 7.
- 34 S. T. T. Ollila, C. Denniston, M. Karttunen and T. Ala-Nissila, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2011, **134**, 064902.
- 35 F. E. Mackay, S. T. T. Ollila and C. Denniston, *Computer Physics Communications*, 2013, **184**, 2021–2031.
- 36 S. T. T. Ollila, C. J. Smith, T. Ala-Nissila and C. Denniston, *Multiscale Modeling & Simulation*, 2013, **11**, 213–243.
- 37 S. T. T. Ollila, C. Denniston and T. Ala-Nissila, *Phys. Rev. E*, 2013, **87**, 050302.
- 38 F. E. Mackay, K. Pastor, M. Karttunen and C. Denniston, *Soft Matter*, 2014, **10**, 8724–8730.
- 39 D. Urbanik, S. Mani Dwivedi and C. Denniston, *The European Physical Journal E*, 2018, **41**, 24.
- 40 M. M. T. Alcanzare, V. Thakore, S. T. T. Ollila, M. Karttunen and T. Ala-Nissila, *Soft Matter*, 2017, **13**, 2148–2154.
- 41 S. T. T. Ollila, C. Denniston, M. Karttunen and T. Ala-Nissila, *Soft Matter*, 2013, **9**, 3478.
- 42 S. T. T. Ollila, C. Denniston, M. Karttunen and T. Ala-Nissila, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2014, **112**, 118301.
- 43 J. M. Polson and J. P. Gallant, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2006, **124**, 184905.
- 44 B. M. Alexander and D. C. Prieve, *Langmuir*, 1987, **3**, 788–795.
- 45 T. Brettschneider, G. Volpe, L. Helden, J. Wehr and C. Bechinger, *Physical Review E - Statistical, Nonlinear, and Soft Matter Physics*, 2011, **83**, 1–9.
- 46 N. A. Frej and D. C. Prieve, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1993, **98**, 7552–7564.
- 47 D. C. Prieve, *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*, 1999, **82**, 93–125.
- 48 D. S. Sholl, M. K. Fenwick, E. Atman and D. C. Prieve, *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2000, **113**, 9268–9278.
- 49 G. Volpe, L. Helden, T. Brettschneider, J. Wehr and C. Bechinger, *Physical Review Letters*, 2010, **104**, 1–4.
- 50 a.J. Goldman, R. Cox and H. Brenner, *Chemical Engineering Science*, 1967, **22**, 653–660.
- 51 B. P. Ho and L. G. Leal, *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 1974, **65**, 365–400.
- 52 A. Alexander-Katz and R. R. Netz, *Macromolecules*, 2008, **41**, 3363–3374.
- 53 D. E. Smith, H. P. Babcock and S. Chu, *Science*, 1999, **283**, 1724–1727.
- 54 C. M. Schroeder, R. E. Teixeira, E. S. G. Shaqfeh and S. Chu, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2005, **95**, 18301.
- 55 F. B. Usabiaga and R. Delgado-Buscalioni, *Macromolecular Theory and Simulations*, 2011, **20**, 466–471.
- 56 M. Phillips, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 1980, **13**, 221.
- 57 J. E. Sadler, *Annual Review of Biochemistry*, 1998, **67**, 395–424.